

Observations from the September 19, 2018, Test with Titan accelerometer and GNSS antenna on the HERB device

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1 Experiment Description

A TitanSMA accelerometer and a GNSS antenna were rotated jointly with the "HERB" experimental platform (Fig. 1) to generate an unbiased displacement time series from real-time GNSS precise point positioning (PPP) and acceleration data by means of a real-time, on-line Kalman filter as described in Bock, Melgar, and Crowell, 2011; Rosenberger et al., 2017.

This document, however, describes the results of an *off-line* analysis. Acceleration data were subjected to a 0.075- 5.0 Hz band-pass filter before processing with the Kalman filter to create similar conditions as in on-line processing.

In general recorded accelerations match the theoretical values well, the problems with a slightly tilting accelerometer platform in earlier experiments did not surface again. The very low turn-rate experiment with $T \approx 12.5s$ may be close to the transition band and be affected by the $0.075Hz$ ($T = 13.7s$) high-pass filter in the real-time implementation.

Both data sets, acceleration and PPP data seem to be well synchronized in UTC time, no further corrections were applied.

A shortcoming of this analysis is the fact that synchronization can only be established once, at the beginning of both data sets, the assumption then is that PPP and accelerometer are perfectly synchronized in time throughout the experiment.

Experiment	Time-slice [s]	T [s]	acceleration [cm/s^2]
1	600-900	12.5	12.6
2	965-1330	8.0	30.0
3	1400-1750	3.8	140.0
4	1815-2175	2.8	256.0
5	2275-2650	2.0	490.0
6	2700-3006	10.0	20.0

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Figure 1: The "HERB" rotating base, the small platform carrying accelerometer and GNSS antenna does not change orientation while it rotates around in a circle. The device was set up to operate with a radius of 0.5 m.

Figure 2: 12.5s experiment. The GNSS PPP data converge to a North-East position, the accelerometer North component is thus mis-aligned by about 45° .

1.1 Experiment One

The HERB platform with a radius of $R = 0.5m$ was rotated in the initial part of the experiment counter-clockwise for about five minutes with a turn period $T \approx 12.5s$, in theory generating centripetal acceleration $a = \omega^2 R \approx 12.6cm/s^2$.

Unfortunately the initial line-up of accelerometer North component with true North, as determined by the GPS shows a mis-match of about 45° as shown in figure 2. For the long turn periods this translates to a larger time gap between the two data-sets, the accelerometer data should then be running ahead of the PPP data, accelerometer absolute north should occur about 3 seconds earlier in the $T \approx 12.5s$ experiment with counter clock-wise turns. This mis-alignment will affect all following experiments but will be less pronounced with smaller turn periods.

Figure 3: North component of acceleration and PPP data from the $T = 12.5s$ experiment

The result in Figure 2 is still acceptable, however, acceleration data had to be subjected to a **sign change** before processing. The best result was achieved setting the accelerometer data standard deviation to $0.1cm/s^2$

2 Experiment Two

The second experiment was run with a turn period of about $8s$, generating a theoretical acceleration of $30cm/s^2$. The result is shown in Figure 5. After initial convergence the long period displacements follow the PPP data, the short period "saw-tooth" pattern may be due to the mis-alignment of GPS and accelerometer. Average PPP standard deviation is $0.8cm$. The standard deviation for the accelerometer was assumed to be $\sigma = 0.05cm/s^2$, again, the acceleration data were **sign reversed**.

Figure 4: Acceleration north component and PPP data from the $T \approx 8s$ experiment, Acceleration runs slightly ahead of the PPP displacements, probably due to initial mis-alignment to true North.

Figure 5: Unbiased displacements and PPP data from the $T \approx 8s$ experiment

3 Experiment Three

For the third experiment the turn period was reduced to $T \approx 3.8s$ corresponding to acceleration of $140cm/s^2$. The final unbiased displacement is shown in Fig. 6. Acceleration data were **sign reversed** and the Kalman filter was driven with an accelerometer standard deviation (the "fudge-factor") of $\sigma = 0.01cm/s^2$. The average PPP standard deviation in this experiment was $0.85cm$. The result after initial convergence seems reasonable.

Figure 6: Unbiased displacements and PPP data from the $T \approx 3.8s$ experiment

4 Experiment Four

The turn period is $T \approx 2.8s$, corresponding to acceleration of $256cm/s^2$, again the average PPP standard deviation is at $0.85cm$, the best result, shown in Figure 7 was obtained sign-reversing acceleration data and setting acceleration standard deviation to $0.05cm/s^2$.

Figure 7: Unbiased displacements and PPP data from the $T \approx 2.8s$ experiment

5 Experiment Five

Experiment five drives the turn period towards the Nyquist frequency imposed by the $1Hz$ sampling rate of the PPP data. This is evident in the result shown in figure 8 where PPP samples show an uneven distribution along the circular path, they gather in the south-east and north-west quadrants. Figure 9 shows only the North component of un-biased displacements and PPP data where the aliasing effect shows as an ambiguous signal which no longer resembles a single frequency periodic. Nevertheless, the acceleration data seem to deliver the additional information, the final un-biased displacements are well aligned with the actual circular path.

Figure 8: Unbiased displacements and PPP data from the $T \approx 2.0s$ experiment

Figure 9: North component unbiased displacements and PPP data from the $T \approx 2.0s$ experiment. PPP data are sampled at $1Hz$ so there are only 2 samples per sinusoid, the Nyquist limit. The aliasing effect becomes apparent in the two-way split pattern no longer resembling a single frequency sinusoid.

6 Experiment Six

The sixth experiment was run with clock-wise movement and a turn period of $T \approx 10s$, acceleration $\approx 20cm/s^2$. PPP average standard deviation is $0.8cm$, acceleration standard deviation was set to $0.05cm/s^2$. The result is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Unbiased displacements and PPP data from the $T = 10s$ experiment with clock-wise turns

7 General Observations

The signal to noise ratio of the acceleration data improves with higher accelerations. Obviously the mechanical noise generated by the platform is independent of the turn period. Experiments three and four thus show a cleaner circular pattern in the un-biased displacements after initial convergence. Apparently the acceleration standard deviation or its squared value, the variance as required in equation 2.7 of Rosenberger et al., 2017 is indeed related to the accelerometer S/N ratio. The best result for the $T \approx 12.5s$ experiment was obtained setting accelerometer standard deviation to $0.1cm/s^2$, the best results from all other experiments with shorter turn periods (and better S/N) were obtained with a standard deviation of $0.05cm/s^2$.

8 Open Questions, Suggestions

The analysis also seems to confirm that the recorded accelerometer data need to be sign reversed in order to conform with a centripetal force keeping the accelerometer on its circular track. Since there are

ambiguities with periodic data, a time-shift of half a period would have the effect of a sign reversal, we should check this in a next experiment moving GPS and accelerometer on a straight track back and forth.

References

- Bock, Y., D. Melgar, and B. W. Crowell (2011). “Real-Time Strong-Motion Broadband Displacements from Collocated GPS and Accelerometers”. In: *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.* 101.6, pp. 2904–2925. DOI: [10.1785/0120110007](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120110007).
- Rosenberger, Andreas et al. (2017). *Kalman Filter Algorithm for the joint Processing of GNSS PPP and Accelerometer Data and EEW parameters from the unbiased displacement time-series*. Tech. rep. ONC, University of Victoria.